

Methane emission from Indonesian high yielding rice cultivars

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ABSTRACT

Rice is an important crop for Indonesian people. Through the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA), rice research on improving productivity and quality has been conducting. The MoA has been producing 4-5 of high yielding rice cultivars every year. But, unfortunately rice cultivation is considered as a contributor of methane emissions. Increasing methane concentration in the atmosphere could lead global warming. A study to identify the quantity of methane emissions from high yielding rice cultivars was conducted in Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute (IAERI). Eight rice cultivars, consisted of one old and famous rice cultivar in farmer's practices (Ciherang) and seven new rice cultivars (Unsoed 1, Hipa 14 SBU, Unsrat 2, Inpari 23, Inpari 28, Inpari Sidenuk and Inpari 16) were used. All of rice cultivars were planted using direct seeded system on July – November 2017. Measurement of methane fluxes was carried out using automatically closed chambers installed permanently in the field. It was observed that that the average methane fluxes varied with different cultivars ranging between 4.22 and 609.68 mg m⁻² day⁻¹. Seasonal emission rates of methane were significantly different among the cultivars. The high methane emissions were observed in the cultivar of Unsoed 1 (340 kg ha⁻¹), followed in Hipa 14 SBU (261 kg ha⁻¹). The intermediate methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Inpari 23 (196 kg ha⁻¹), Inpari 16 (189 kg ha⁻¹) and Inpari Sidenuk (188 kg ha⁻¹). The lower methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Ciherang (184 kg ha⁻¹), Unsrat 2 (164 kg ha⁻¹) and Inpari 28 (147 kg ha⁻¹). The rice yield was not significant among rice cultivars. The highest and lowest rice yields were 6.18 and 5.57 t ha⁻¹ produced by the cultivars of Inpari Sidenuk and Inpari 28, respectively.

Keywords: methane, rice variety, high yield, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture sector contribute to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions around 6-14%, mainly by CH₄ and N₂O emission. CH₄ and N₂O are the two most important GHGs from agriculture with the 100 years Global Warming Potential (GWP) of 34 and 293 CO₂-eq, respectively (IPCC, 2013). It is reported that around 15–20% of global anthropogenic methane emission is from paddy field

(Smith et al, 2007). The emission of CH₄ into the atmosphere depends on several factors such as water management, amendment of organic and inorganic fertilizers, rice varietal characteristics and soil environment (Mitra et al., 1999).

There are large differences in CH₄ emissions between fields with different rice cultivars because of the plant differences in methane production, oxidation and transport capacities (Kaushik et al., 2008; Lou et al., 2008 and Ma et al., 2010). The CH₄ emitted by plant-mediated transport accounted for more than 90% of the total emissions (Sass et al, 1990) and depends on aerenchyma system among rice cultivars (Inubushi et al, 2003). Setyanto et al (2004) stated that the use of selected rice cultivar could release lower CH₄ without decline the yield. Differences of rice cultivars to release CH₄ depends on its characteristic and agro-ecological condition Yu et al (2013) suggested that there was a large potential to mitigate CH₄ emissions by rice cultivar selection. The objective of this study was to identify the quantity of methane emissions from high yielding rice cultivars cultivated in Indonesia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental design and crop management

Field experiment was conducted in the Research Station of Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute (IAERI) located at Sidomukti, Subdistrict of Jaken, district of Pati, Central Java Province. The location lies between 111°10'E longitude and 6°45'S latitude. The area is dominated by rainfed rice, with average of rainfall, maximum and minimum of temperature, daily temperature and solar radiation during the experiment was 303 mm, 42°C, 23.0°C, 37.3°C and 62970 Cal cm⁻², respectively. The soil at the experiment site was sandy loam and low organic matter. Table 1 presents the physico-chemical properties of the experimental soil.

Eight of high yielding rice cultivars, namely Ciherang, Unsoed 1, Hipa 14 SBU, Unsrat 2, Inpari 23, Inpari 28, Inpari Sidenuk and Inpari 16 were planted by direct seeded in plots of 6 m x 6 m with three replications in randomized block design (RBD). These rice cultivars differed in their growth characteristics (Table 2). Chemical fertilizers were applied at 120:45:60 kg N:P₂O₅:K₂O ha⁻¹. One-third dose of urea, half dose K₂O and full dose of P₂O₅ were applied at the active tillering growth stage. The other one-third doses of urea and half dose of K₂O were applied at the maximum tillering or panicle initiation stages. Flooding water was maintained at 5 cm above soil surface during plant growing and the field was dried before harvesting.

Methane flux measurement

Methane fluxes were determined from 16 until 97 day after sowing (DAS). Gas samples were collected with using the close chamber method. Chambers of 105 cm length, 105 cm width and 125 cm height made of acrylic transparent sheets were used. The chamber was operated automatically based on distributed control system during rice growing. Gases were taken on interval time of 4, 8, 12 and 16 minutes after closing chamber.

Methane concentration in the gas samples was determined by using a Gas Chromatograph (GC 2014, Shimadzu) equipped with a Flame Ionization Detector (FID). The methane flux was calculated using the following equation:

$$E = \frac{dc}{dt} \times \frac{Vch}{Ach} \times \frac{mW}{mV} \times \frac{273.2}{(273.2 + T)}$$

Where E is flux of CH₄ and N₂O (mg m⁻² day⁻¹), dc/dt is difference of gas concentration per time (ppm minute⁻¹), Vch is volume of chamber (m³), Ach is large of chamber (m²), The size of chamber was 105 cm x 105 cm x 125 cm, mW is weight of gases molecule (g), mV is volume of gases molecule (22.41 l) and T is average of temperature during gases sampling (°C).

Plant parameters and statistics

Number of tillers and plant height were recorded at different plant phase (active tiller, maximum tiller, heading, milky and maturity), while grain yield and rice straw were recorded at the time of harvest.

The Minitab 16.0 version was used to calculate the means for methane emissions and plant parameters. Tukey's (p<0.05) was done to find out the differences between the recorded parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Observed characteristics of rice cultivars during plant growing

Rice cultivars	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Growth duration (days)	Maximum height (cm)	Tiller number per hill
Ciherang	5,81	100	96	14-16
Unsoed 1	5,87	106	>100	17-19
Hipa 14 SBU	5,88	110	>100	14-18
Unsrat 2	5,64	105	>100	10-15
Inpari 23	5,85	105	96	11-14
Inpari 28	5,57	105	100	13-17
Inpari Sidenuk	6,18	104	98	14-19
Inpari 16	6,07	100	92	15-16

Figure 1. Methane fluxes from rice cultivars of Unsoed 1 and Hipa 14 SBU

Methane fluxes from different rice cultivars are presented on Figures 1, 2 and 3. Figure 1 shows the pattern of methane fluxes from rice cultivars of Unsoed 1 and Hipa 14 SBU. The maximum methane fluxes were 609.68 and 526.87 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$ for the cultivars of Unsoed 1 and Hipa 14 SBU, respectively. The average of methane fluxes from those cultivars were 317.54 and 237.09 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$.

Figure 2. Methane fluxes from rice cultivars of Inpari 23, Inpari 16 and Inpari Sidenuk

Figure 2 shows the patterns of methane fluxes from Inpari 23, Inpari 16 and Inpari Sidenuk with the maximum methane fluxes of 345.72, 462.65 and 337.35 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$, respectively. The methane fluxes average of those cultivars were 186.44, 179.72 and 186.67 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the pattern of methane fluxes from rice cultivars of Ciherang, Unsrat 2 and Inpari 28. The peaks of fluxes were 455.14, 334.86 and 390.33 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$, and average methane fluxes were 187.17, 157.43 and 146.08 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$, respectively.

Figure 3. Methane fluxes from rice cultivars of Ciherang, Unsrat 2 and Inpari 28

Seasonal methane emission showed significant difference among the rice cultivars (Table 2). The highest and lowest methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Unsoed 1 and Inpari 28, respectively. We have categorized the rice cultivars into three groups as high, intermediate and low methane emissions. The high methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Unsoed 1 (340 kg ha^{-1}) and Hipa 14 SBU (261 kg ha^{-1}). The intermediate methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Inpari 23 (196 kg ha^{-1}), Inpari 16 (189 kg ha^{-1}) and Inpari Sidenuk (188 kg ha^{-1}). The lower methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Ciherang (184 kg ha^{-1}), Unsrat 2 (164 kg ha^{-1}) and Inpari 28 (147 kg ha^{-1}). We found that seasonal methane emissions has a positive correlation with effective number of tillers ($r^2 = 0.403$, $n = 16$), plant height ($r^2 = 0.378$, $n = 16$) and aboveground biomass ($r^2 = 0.658$, $n = 16$). Rice yield (grains) was not significantly different among the rice cultivars. The highest yield was produced by cultivar of Inpari Sidenuk and the lowest by Inpari 28.

Table 2. Seasonal methane emission, plant parameters and rice yield

Rice cultivars	Methane emission (kg ha ⁻¹ season ⁻¹)	Effective of tillering number	Plant height (cm)	Aboveground biomass (t ha ⁻¹)	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Ciherang	184 c	13 bc	95 bc	5.91 a	5.81 a
Unsoed 1	340 a	16 a	105 a	8.34 a	5.87 a
Hipa 14 SBU	261 b	13 bc	103 a	7.53 a	5.88 a
Unsrat 2	164 c	11 c	100 ab	5.73 a	5.64 a
Inpari 23	196 bc	12 bc	95 bc	5.93 a	5.85 a
Inpari 28	147 c	14 ab	99 ab	6.93 a	5.57 a
Inpari Sidenuk	188 bc	14 ab	100 ab	6.28 a	6.18 a
Inpari 16	189 bc	13 bc	91 c	6.85 a	6.07 a

Means followed by same letter do not significant different

Rice cultivars significantly contributed to methane emissions. Different cultivar may play an important role in controlling methane emissions from rice field (Gutierrez et al., 2013). We found that each rice cultivar has different pattern on methane fluxes, particularly for high, intermediate and lower rice cultivars groups. The high methane cultivars showed increase fluxes sharply on 30 DAS and continued to generative phase.

CONCLUSIONS

The high methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Unsoed 1 and Hipa 14 SBU. While the intermediate methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Inpari 23, Inpari 16 and Inpari Sidenuk. The lower methane emissions were observed in the cultivars of Ciherang, Unsrat 2 and Inpari 28. The rice yield was not significant among rice cultivars. The highest and lowest rice yield were 6.18 and 5.57 t ha⁻¹ produced by variety of Inpari Sidenuk and Inpari 28, respectively.

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